

Feasibility Study: Soluble Protein Expression Measured by HiBiT in *Escherichia coli* and *Pichia pastoris*

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About the Align Foundation

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Introduction

The reliable prediction of soluble protein expression remains a major bottleneck in synthetic biology and protein engineering. To address this challenge, we believe a large, high-quality dataset of soluble protein expression across diverse hosts, covering tens or hundreds of thousands of open reading frames (ORFs) is required. This dataset can serve as the foundation for training machine learning models to guide future protein expression efforts, as outlined in Baranowski et al¹.

A critical first step in this effort is establishing scalable and standardized assay methods that can generate expression data that is **shareable, reproducible, and extensible** across expression systems. To this end, we conducted a feasibility study to evaluate the suitability of the HiBiT luminescence-based reporter assay, which utilizes an 11-amino acid peptide tag that associates with a complementing LgBiT subunit, to form the NanoLuc luciferase enzyme for high-throughput quantification of soluble protein expression.

In this work, we aimed to test the feasibility of using the HiBiT assay for assessing protein expression in two microbial hosts: *Escherichia coli* and *Pichia pastoris*. These hosts represent distinct expression systems, bacterial and yeast, that serve as an ideal starting point to evaluate cross-organismal assay

performance. The goal of this study is to determine whether a workflow involving a HiBiT-tagged approach to measuring soluble protein can reliably quantify expression levels across these systems and provide the necessary scalability and robustness required for broader implementation. Furthermore, protein expression measured by HiBiT was compared with 1) published SDS-PAGE expression ranking (whole cell lysate) of the same ORFs expressed in BL21(DE3) from a closely related pET vector² and 2) red fluorescence from mScarlet-I3 codon variants. We hypothesized that expression as measured by SDS-PAGE and red fluorescence would correlate with expression measured via the HiBiT assay.

For more details on the overall vision and scope of this project, please refer to our project proposal, "**A strategy for scalable data collection of soluble protein expression in diverse hosts**"¹.

Methods

General Strategy and Expression Strains

A common *E. coli* expression strain and an open source version of a common *P. pastoris* strain were used as hosts for cytosolic protein expression in this study. The same DNA sequences of 30

ORFs were expressed in *E. coli* and *P. pastoris* from host specific expression cassettes. In *E. coli*, a pET28a³ plasmid was used, and integration at the pAOX1 locus was used in *P. pastoris*. Table 1 provides details about the expression strains, genetic cassettes and ORF breakdown.

Table 1: Summary of Feasibility Design (modified from Align’s original project proposal¹)

Expression strains	Key Features	Genetic cassette	ORFs Tested	Unique strains to be generated
<i>E. coli</i> BL21 AI F- <i>ompT hsdSB</i> (rB-, mB-) <i>gal dcm</i> araB::T7RNAP-tetA Strain obtained from: ThermoFisher Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arabinose-inducible T7 RNA polymerase expression Fast growth- Doubling time ~20 minutes Protease deficient (lon and ompT) 	pET28a; IPTG + arabinose inducible expression	18 diverse ORFs from Boël <i>et al.</i> 12 codon varied mScarlet-I3 The same 30 ORFs were cloned into pET28a for <i>E. coli</i> expression, or integrated at pAOX1 for <i>P. pastoris</i> expression.	30 ORFs were cloned with both N- and C-terminal HiBiT tags = 60 total unique strains
<i>P. pastoris</i> OPENPichia NCYC 2543 <i>hoc1tr-1</i> Strain obtained from: https://openpichia.sites.vib.be/en	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strain generated and described in Claes <i>et al.</i> Genome sequenced type strain derived from NCYC 2543 Near-identical to NRRL Y-11430, the commercialized and difficult to license industrial strain Hoc1 truncation increases transformation efficiency up to NRRL Y-11430 Doubling time ~60-120 minutes Open-access strain and cloning materials 	Integration at pAOX1; methanol inducible expression		30 ORFs were cloned with both N- and C-terminal his tags = 60 total unique strains

ORF selection

To assess the dynamic range of heterologous protein expression, we assembled an expression ladder composed of 30 ORFs (see Table 2 for a summary and Table 3 for detailed ORF information; full ORF sequences are included as a Genbank file in the supplemental information). This set included 12 distinct codon-optimized sequences of the fluorescent protein mScarlet-I3 and 18 diverse ORFs selected from Boël *et al.*². The 18 diverse ORFs were selected to span a range of expression as measured by

SDS-PAGE in Boël *et al.* Each ORF was fused to a HiBiT tag via a glycine-serine linker on both the N- and C-terminus, yielding 60 expression constructs per host.

Table 2 and following text are modified from our project proposal.¹

ORFs were analyzed for the following restriction enzyme cut sites: BsaI, BsmBI, NotI, PaeCI, PmeI, and SapI. To facilitate GoldenGate cloning and other downstream applications, if any of these restriction enzyme cut sites were found, synonymous codons were substituted to remove them.

Table 2: Summary of Control ORFs for Feasibility (from proposal)

ORF set	Purpose	Pro	Con
Diverse ORF expression ladder (Boël <i>et al.</i>)	Ladder of diverse ORFs from literature with range of expression in <i>E. coli</i> . Does HiBiT recapitulate SDS-PAGE based ladder of expression?	Validated expression in <i>E. coli</i> . Sequence variation tests protein length and diversity in assay context.	Assay failure may be due to difference in ORF seq and not the method. Unknown expression in <i>P. pastoris</i> .
Codon varied fluorescent protein (mScarlet-I3)	Predict that there will be a range of expression after varying codon usage to generate a ladder of expression from unchanged amino acid sequence.	Fluorescence provides a quick orthogonal readout to HiBiT. Easy to design and order. ORF is the same size and function and therefore well controlled.	No <i>a priori</i> expression levels to benchmark against.

Diverse ORFs

Part of the ORF ladder was derived from a previously published large-scale expression study by Boël *et al.*². In that study, 6,348 genes from 171 phylogenetically diverse organisms including *E. coli*, mammals, archaeobacteria, and 151 different eubacterial species were tested for expression in *E. coli* BL21 (DE3). The ORFs were not codon-optimized and were expressed from a pET21 vector in a host strain co-expressing a tRNA for the AGA arginine codon.

In that work, protein expression was evaluated via visual inspection of whole-cell lysates run on Coomassie-stained SDS-PAGE gels. Each protein was assigned an integer expression score from 0 to 5, where 0 represented undetectable expression and 5 indicated the protein was the most abundant in the lysate. For this feasibility dataset, three proteins from each of the six expression bins were selected, ensuring a representation of low to high expressors. The selected ORFs spanned a range of lengths (300–3000 nucleotides) and originated from diverse taxa.

Table 3: Diverse ORF details

UniProt ID	Gene Name (Boël et al)	Expression level (Boël et al)	Gene length (nt)	Top BLAST hit- species result
Q1MG77	RIR163A	0	300	<i>Rhizobium leguminosarum</i> bv. <i>trifolii</i>
A0A8C6I9X1	MmR383	0	1494	<i>Mus musculus</i>
Q82Y16	NeR156	0	2580	<i>Nitrosomonas europaea</i> ATCC 19718
Q6DI29	EwR33	1	333	<i>Pectobacterium atrosepticum</i>
Q9KBP4	BhR103	1	1551	<i>Halalkalibacterium halodurans</i> C-125
O52682	VR98	1	1947	<i>Thermotoga maritima</i>
A0A6I5E7S6	SvR106	2	303	<i>Streptomyces avermitilis</i>
A0A368UVV4	MqR106	2	1512	<i>Marinobacter nauticus</i>
Q880F2	PsR158	2	2244	<i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> pv. <i>tomato</i>
Q987X8	MIR21	3	303	<i>Mesorhizobium japonicum</i>
Q9HLK5	TaR26	3	1491	<i>Thermoplasma acidophilum</i>
Q3Z5I1	ER475	3	2466	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Q8PTY0	MaR237	4	300	<i>Methanosarcina mazei</i>
P52043	ER458	4	1503	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Q48AQ8	CsR66	4	2349	<i>Colwellia psychrerythraea</i> 34H
Q928T4	LkR138B	5	300	<i>Listeria innocua</i>
Q6FF41	AsR115	5	1509	<i>Acinetobacter baylyi</i>
A0A494WX46	QsR101	5	2385	<i>[Clostridium] scindens</i> ATCC 35704

To ensure biosafety compliance, all selected sequences were screened for potential biorisk using the Common Mechanism screening package developed by IBBIS³. All candidate ORFs passed this screen and were included in the final expression ladder. Full details on each ORF including expression bin, sequence length, and source organism are provided in the Supplemental Materials. This table is a small subset of Boël *et al.*'s Supplementary Data 2², with new columns added for the UniProt ID and the species associated with the top BLAST hit for the sequence.

Codon varied fluorescent protein ORFs

The mScarlet-I3 DNA sequence⁵ was processed via IDT's codon optimizer to generate a library of codon differentiated FPs. Specifically, it was run through the codon optimizer 6 times for *E. coli* B strain and 6 times for *Pichia pastoris*⁶ yielding 12 distinct DNA sequences all with the same amino acid sequence. Nucleotide sequences are provided in Supplemental information.

Genetic constructs for protein expression

E. coli plasmids

All ORFs with N- or C-terminal linker and HiBiT were cloned into the pET28a³ plasmid. Strains were transformed and validated via sequencing. For *E. coli*, 59/60 plasmids were successfully constructed using DNA synthesized by Twist Bioscience (South San Francisco, CA) and cloned by Clutch Biosciences (Burlingame, CA). Genbank files of *E. coli* plasmids can be found in the supplemental information.

Pichia plasmids

All 30 ORFs with N- or C-terminal linker and HiBiT were first cloned into the pPpT4⁷ plasmid vector in *E. coli*. Then, they were miniprepmed and linearized at the PmeI site. Linearized DNA was used in *P. pastoris* transformations resulting in integration at the AOX1 promoter (Figure 1). For *P. pastoris*, 60 plasmids were successfully constructed by Ginkgo Bioworks (Boston, MA) and used for transformation into *P. pastoris*. Genbank files of *Pichia* plasmids can be found in the supplemental information.

HiBiT Assay

Protein abundance was measured using a protein complementation assay (PCA) called HiBiT that utilizes a split NanoLuc luciferase. Proteins of interest were N- or C-terminally tagged with the 11 amino acid HiBiT peptide tag (a portion of NanoLuc). The HiBiT complementing LgBiT polypeptide and furimazine substrate were added after cell lysis. When HiBiT and LgBiT interact, they reconstitute the luciferase enzyme, NanoLuc. Luminescence intensity has previously been reported to be proportional to the abundance of the HiBiT tagged protein of interest⁸.

HiBiT is an attractive assay to measure soluble protein expression in an arrayed format because it utilizes a small tag (11 amino acids), can be measured using a plate reader, and does not require extensive sample preparation. Furthermore, because this assay relies on a kit⁹, this minimizes the potential for variation in reagents, increasing the likelihood of reproducibility. Interestingly, most published HiBiT data is in mammalian cells, including the manufacturer's current protocol¹⁰. There are a few examples in literature of this assay being utilized in bacteria and yeast. In lactic acid bacteria¹¹ and budding yeast S288c¹², mechanical lysis (bead beating) followed by use of the extracellular detection kit has

been used. HiBiT has also been used for protein transport assays in bacteria^{13–16} and for pathogen detection via phage¹⁷ however these either did not require lysis or utilized phage for cell lysis. Since there is limited data about the use of HiBiT in microbes for measuring soluble protein expression, we sought to conduct a feasibility study for use of this assay in *E. coli* and *P. pastoris*. All data was generated by Ginkgo Bioworks (Boston, MA).

Biological replicates (bioreps) are defined as independent colonies picked after strain transformation. Technical replicates are separately cultured copies of the same biological replicate. Three bioreps per strain for *E. coli* and four for *P. pastoris* were grown and measured for growth by OD600 and fluorescence of mScarlet-I3 was measured. A single replicate of each biorep was measured for protein expression via luminescence (HiBiT).

Screening Protocol (Figure 2).

This is an overview of the screening workflow used for *E. coli*. The *P. pastoris* workflow is similar. The screening workflow consists of four main steps:

1. Build strains by transforming DNA into a host strain.
2. Grow cells and produce protein.
3. Lyse cells and centrifuge to precipitate insoluble material.
4. Perform the HiBiT assay by adding LgBiT reagent and substrate to supernatant and measuring luminescent readout.

Figure 2: High-level experimental workflow

Briefly, Step 2 (Figure 2, Produce protein) encompasses strain growth from glycerol stocks, through induction of protein expression to the terminal OD and sampling time point. Cells were inoculated from glycerol stocks and grown in “preculture” plates. After one day of growth, OD600 and red fluorescence (RFP) were measured for each biorep (3 total measurements per genotype for *E. coli* and 4 for *P. pastoris*). Additionally, green fluorescence (GFP) was measured for *E. coli* samples. Cells were subcultured into production media, which includes the inducer for expression (either IPTG and arabinose for pET28a in BL21

(DE3)-AI or methanol for *P. pastoris* with integration at the AOX1 promoter). After ~18 or ~72 hours of “production” growth (*E. coli* and *P. pastoris* respectively), OD600, RFP and GFP were measured. Once completed, the cells were pelleted and lysed (Figure 2, Step 3: Lyse cells). The lysate was carried to the Step 4: HiBiT readout, where the complementing LgBiT fragment and furimazine substrate are added and luminescence was measured per biorep following the detailed protocol attached. (Figure 3, Figure 4)

Figure 3: *E. coli* experimental workflow

Figure 4: *P. pastoris* experimental workflow

Results

Strain Construction

In *E. coli*, 59 out of 60 plasmids were successfully cloned and confirmed via sequencing, with the exception of the N-terminally HiBIT-tagged Ner156 construct, which could not be cloned.

All *P. pastoris* strains were successfully transformed. Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) long-read sequencing was performed on two biological replicates per strain, revealing that approximately 75% of strains had the desired genotype, defined as single-copy integration at the AOX1 locus (Figure 5, *P. pastoris* ONT results).

Figure 5: ONT characterization of *P. pastoris* strains built

Growth by Optical Density

Growth during the expression protocol differed between species. In *E. coli*, optical density (OD) measurements at the preculture stage showed low variability (Supplemental Figure 1A), while at the production time point showed significant variability across strains (Figure 6A).

In *P. pastoris*, contamination was observed in uninoculated wells (Supplemental Figure 1C). Compared to *E. coli*, there was less range in OD of the production cultures (Figure 6B). In line with increased culture time, OD values were generally higher at the production time point (72h) than at preculture (24h) (Supplemental Figure 1B).

Figure 6: Production Culture OD600 data (A) *E. coli* ODs. Positive = pT7.3lac-alt1_BD2-mCherry-HiBiT, Negative = pT7-BCD2-dasherG-FP, Standard = HiBiT assay kit standard, Library (blank) = not inoculated but located where library strains could be, Blank = not inoculated; (B) *P. pastoris* ODs. Positive = mScar13-Ppl-C-terminal, Negative = a non-engineered parent strain, Blank = not inoculated. The asterisks mark outliers calculated using Iglewicz and Hoaglin's Modified Z Score. Outliers were excluded from the box plots.

HiBiT-Based Protein Expression

Protein expression, as calculated from the luminescence signal and calibrated to a HaloTag protein standard curve, showed a broad range of concentrations across *E. coli* strains (Figure 7A).

In *P. pastoris*, protein expression also spanned a wide concentration range; however, several strains exhibited large variability between biological replicates, suggesting potential differences in lysis efficiency, expression stability, or workflow variability (Figure 7B).

Figure 7: HiBiT-based read-out of soluble protein expression. (A) *E. coli* data, 100x dilution. Positive= pT7.3lac-*alt1*_BD2-mCherry-HiBiT, Negative = pT7-BCD2-dasherGFP, Standard = HiBiT assay kit standard, Library (blank) = not inoculated but located where library strains could be, Blank = not inoculated; (B) *P. pastoris* data, 5x dilution. Positive= mScarlet3-Ppl-C-terminal, Negative = a non-engineered parent strain, Blank = not inoculated. The asterisks mark outliers calculated using Iglewicz and Hoaglin's Modified Z Score. Outliers were excluded from the box plots.

Inducible Red Fluorescence from mScarlet-13

Strains expressing mScarlet-13 displayed inducible red fluorescence in both species (Supplemental Figure 2). Similarly to

the HiBiT measurements, the *E. coli* fluorescence showed low variation while in *P. pastoris*, biological replicate measurements exhibited a higher degree of spread (Figure 8).

Figure 8: mScarlet-13 Fluorescence of Production cultures. (A) *E. coli* fluorescence; (B) *P. pastoris* fluorescence. The asterisks mark outliers calculated using Iglewicz and Hoaglin's Modified Z Score. Outliers were excluded from the box plots.

Correlation Between HiBiT and Growth

Calculated protein concentration did not strongly correlate with OD in either organism (Figure 9). In *E. coli*, the correlation between HiBiT and OD was weak ($R^2 = 0.165$), while in *P. pastoris*, the correlation was negligible ($R^2 = 0.00005$).

Figure 9: OD600 vs HiBiT signal. (A) *E. coli* only, 100x dilution, library; **(B)** *P. pastoris* only, 5x dilution, library.

Correlation Between HiBIT Expression and mScarlet-I3 Fluorescence

HiBIT luminescence correlated with red fluorescence (mScarlet-I3) in both organisms (Figure 10A, 11B). In *E. coli*, the correlation between HiBIT and red fluorescence was strong ($R^2 =$

0.720, Figure 10A). In *P. pastoris*, the correlation was apparent but not as strong as in *E. coli* ($R^2 = 0.399$, Figure 10B). When the strains were separated by N- and C-terminally tagged mScarlet-I3, the correlations with HiBIT in *P. pastoris* were stronger ($R^2 = 0.54$, $R^2 = 0.684$ for C- and N-terminally tagged respectively, Figure 10C, 11D).

Figure 10: HiBIT signal vs. mScarlet-I3 Fluorescence. (A) *E. coli* HiBIT vs RFP (positive control strain in grey, 100x dilution); (B) *P. pastoris* HiBIT vs RFP, 5x dilution; (C) *P. pastoris* HiBIT N-terminal only; (D) *P. pastoris* C-terminal HiBIT only

Correlation Between HiBiT Expression and SDS-PAGE

HiBiT luminescence was compared to previously published SDS-PAGE expression rankings in *E. coli* only (Figure 11). The correlation was not strong, with $R^2 = 0.141$.

Figure 11: HiBiT vs SDS-PAGE 2 (*E. coli* only, 100x dilution)

Correlation Between HiBiT Expression and Protein Molecular Weight

HiBiT luminescence did correlate with the molecular weight of the expressed ORFs for both organisms (Figure 12).

Figure 12: HiBiT-based expression vs. molecular weight of protein (kDa). (A) *E. coli*, 100x dilution (B) *P. pastoris*, 5x dilution

HiBiT Assay Robustness and Matrix Effects

Assay validation performed by Ginkgo Bioworks confirmed that the HiBiT standard curve retained linearity and selectivity across multiple background conditions. In *E. coli*, HiBiT readout performance was unaffected by lysate matrix components, validating the use of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) as a diluent

in the standard curve (Supplemental Table 1, Supplementary Figure 3). Similarly, no matrix effects were observed from *P. pastoris* lysates, confirming PBS as an appropriate diluent for HiBiT quantification in both systems.

Discussion

In this study, we evaluated the performance of the HiBiT assay to quantify soluble protein expression in two heterologous hosts, *Escherichia coli* and *Pichia pastoris*, for a panel of 30 open reading frames (ORFs). The ORFs included 12 recoded variants of the red fluorescent protein mScarlet-I3. Our results provide insights into the utility and limitations of HiBiT-based quantification in these microbial systems and guide future directions for scalable expression profiling.

Comparative Performance in *E. coli* and *P. pastoris*

E. coli demonstrated robust and quantifiable HiBiT expression across the majority of ORFs, with a dynamic range spanning three orders of magnitude. The reproducibility and resolution of the HiBiT signal in *E. coli* enabled the stratification of proteins into a statistically distinguishable expression ladder. This expression ladder indicates that HiBiT could be a promising tool for screening large libraries in *E. coli*.

Expression measurements in *P. pastoris* were noisier. We hypothesize that variability beyond technical noise could have been impacted by genotypic heterogeneity introduced during strain construction. Approximately 25% of transformed strains deviated from the intended single-copy genomic integration, exhibiting either multiple insertions or off-target integrations (Figure 5). Given the known dosage sensitivity of gene expression in yeast, such deviations may introduce confounding variance in observed HiBiT signals (Supplemental Figure 4). This complicates downstream analyses in high-throughput formats.

Effects of Tag Placement and Correlation with Orthogonal Measures

The positional effect of the HiBiT tag on protein termini varied based on protein. In *E. coli*, tag orientation (N- versus C-terminal) had protein-specific impacts on signal intensity, suggesting context-dependent influences on folding, stability, or tag accessibility. This positional dependency was also observed in *P. pastoris*, though assay noise diminished the interpretability of trends.

Importantly, HiBiT signals were positively correlated with mScarlet fluorescence in both systems. This correlation supports

the validity of using this orthogonal readout for cross-validation and suggests that HiBiT may serve as a semi-quantitative proxy for protein abundance under appropriate conditions.

Comparison with SDS-PAGE-Based Expression Classification

We further compared HiBiT measurements with previously published SDS-PAGE-based expression rankings from Boël et al.². Although global correlations were weak, ORFs categorized as “5” (highest expression) by Boël et al. on average displayed significantly higher HiBiT signals relative to lower-ranked groups (buckets 0–4) (Figure 11). However, all other expression buckets from Boël et al did not follow this trend, suggesting that Boël classifications may not reflect the soluble expression measure by HiBiT under our experimental conditions.

Assay and Analytical Considerations

Several methodological observations emerged from the *P. pastoris* assay. Culturing procedure steps led to contamination in media-only wells, warranting protocol refinements (see Supplementary Fig. 1C *P. pastoris* OD in media only wells). Additionally, because optical density (OD) measurements did not correlate with HiBiT signal in either host, protein expression normalization by OD was not performed. There was also no detectable relationship between the molecular weight of the expressed proteins and the resulting HiBiT signal in either host system (Figure 12).

Conclusion

Collectively, these results highlight both the potential and the limitations of the HiBiT-based screening workflow for quantifying soluble protein expression in microbial systems. While the *E. coli* workflow offers a robust and interpretable platform for high-throughput screening using HiBiT, its application in *P. pastoris* will require improved control of strain genotypes and protocol optimization to realize similar utility. Future work should focus on optimizing transformation protocols, validating strain integrity post-integration, and refining assay conditions to mitigate technical noise.

Future Directions

Although the HiBiT assay has demonstrated utility for quantifying soluble protein expression, our findings highlight several limitations that must be addressed before the method can be considered a scalable and standardized platform for cross-system protein expression profiling.

Our first execution does not yet meet the criteria of being fully **reproducible or extensible** across host organisms or experimental contexts but it has identified protocol areas that require improvement. While the HiBiT assay itself is an effective measure of protein concentration, the workflow's susceptibility to technical variability, especially in transformation, culturing, and lysis of *P. pastoris*, highlights the need for continued development toward a more robust protocol with the goal of high reproducibility. In particular, cross-contamination issues during plate processing (notably in media-only wells) must be resolved (see Supplementary Fig. 1C on *P. pastoris* cross-contamination).

Another critical challenge is the **scalability** of the current assay format. The use of singleplex assays, while providing high-resolution measurements, limits throughput and increases the labor and time required to process large sample sets. Transitioning toward **pooled formats** or adopting miniaturized high-throughput platforms could significantly enhance efficiency and enable broader application in large-scale expression studies.

Ultimately, achieving a truly scalable and interoperable protein expression assay will likely require not only optimization of the existing protein expression workflow, but also exploring alternative assay methodologies. These improvements are essential to enable reliable, high-throughput screening of protein expression across diverse biological systems.

Acknowledgements:

Myat Lin for contribution to *Pichia* genome sequence analysis, Tessa Alexanian at The International Biosecurity and Biosafety Initiative for Science (IBBIS) for biosecurity screening of expression ORFs, Ginkgo Bioworks for all data generation, and the Align Foundation Team for supporting this work.

Declaration

The parts of the introduction, methods, results, conclusion, and future directions sections were initially drafted using OpenAI's ChatGPT and subsequently edited by the authors.

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